

Substituent specific bisbenzimidazole binding towards AT-rich DNA[†]

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DNA minor groove is the target of a large number of non-covalent binding agents. The small molecules bind with DNA by means of a combination of directed hydrogen bonding to base pair edges, van der Waals interactions with the minor groove walls and generalized electrostatic interactions. Molecular recognition of DNA by small molecules and proteins is a fundamental problem in structural biology and drug design. Understanding of recognition of novel minor groove binders (MGBs) in sequence-specific way at the level of successful prediction of binding modes and site selectivity will be instrumental for improvements in the design and synthesis of new molecules as potent and selective gene-regulatory drugs. The binding characteristics of MGBs are important for the rational design and development of novel ones. The spectroscopic characterization of four novel bisbenzimidazoles reveals that DNA binding is affected by its chemical constituents like aliphatic chain length as well as nature of functionalizations. The BPPMF with longer carbon chain stands out as compared to MPPMF and APPMF having shorter carbon chains to be more effectively packed in minor groove of DNA. The stoichiometry, binding affinity of BPPMF: DNA complex was calculated from UV-titration with decamer duplex DNA, showed better binding with an order of 10 as compared to parent analogue Hoechst 33342. Molecular docking study correlates the trends obtained from experimental data. These findings could be useful in the design of MGBs for therapeutic purposes.

Keywords: Bisbenzimidazole, minor groove binder (MGB), B-DNA, spectroscopy, molecular docking.

Introduction

It is reported in literature that DNA minor groove binding ligands have potential for treating neoplastic and infectious diseases. Some of the DNA minor groove binding ligands are DAPI, Distamycin A, Netropsin, Hoechst 33342 etc.¹⁻⁸. Drugs recognizing specific regions of DNA could achieve high selectivity and efficacy, because they interrupt the biochemistry of a cell at fundamental levels of DNA replication and transcription^{9,10}. Hoechst 33258 [5-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-2-[2'-(4-hydroxy)-5'-benzimidazolyl]benzimidazole] and Hoechst 33342 [5-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-2-[2'-(4-ethoxy)-5'-benzimidazolyl]benzimidazole] are well known scavengers of free radicals which act as radioprotectors^{11,12} thereby reducing the induction of DNA damage in solution and in cells under certain conditions. On the other side, these agents are also known to act as antitumor agents by topoisomerase I and II inhibition^{13,14}. Hoechst 33342 is also known to possess antimicrobial, antifungal and antiviral activities. The

mutagenic, clastogenic and cytotoxic effects of these ligands limit their use as radioprotectors in humans.

Based on the existing knowledge, new ligands were designed and synthesized on the basis of Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) and molecular modeling studies earlier reported from our laboratory¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Two ligands were designed, one was bisbenzimidazole (DMA) [5-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-2-[2'-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-5'-benzimidazolyl]benzimidazole] and other was terbenzimidazole (TBZ) [5-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-2-[2'-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-5'-benzimidazolyl]benzimidazole] with increased lipophilicity and improved sequence length recognition and sequence specificity. DMA and TBZ bear bisubstitution on phenyl ring, whereas parent molecules have single substitution on the phenyl ring. DMA has two methoxy groups *ortho* to each other whereas TBZ has a hydroxyl group at the *para*-position and a methoxy group *ortho* to it. Methoxy groups on phenyl ring increase the lipophilicity as well as the

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DNA duplex stability. Presence of electron donating groups on the phenyl ring increases the electron density on the nitrogens of the imidazole ring. The 'NH' group of the imidazole ring is very well reported to have a strong H-bond interaction with the bases of DNA hence the increasing of electron density at Nitrogen increases the feasibility of H-bond formation between NH-imidazole and electronegative 'O'-atoms of nucleic acid bases. Interaction of these two analogues with DNA was analyzed by solution studies using Ultraviolet (UV), fluorescence spectroscopy, equilibrium binding titrations, and gel mobility shift assays. These Hoechst analogues found to be better radioprotectors with decreased cytotoxicity toward mammalian cells as compared to the parent molecules. It is reported that at physiological pH, the nitrogen atom of piperazine moiety bearing a positive charge interacts with GC site of DNA molecule and showed GC tolerance. Different piperazine derivatives will be synthesized to analyze the effect of binding of these Hoechst analogues with DNA molecule. *In vitro* studies were done on cancer cell lines in our laboratory earlier which revealed that DMA and many other Hoechst analogues show less cytotoxicity profiles compared to parent molecules (Hoechst 33258 and Hoechst 33342) that warrant *in vivo* studies on pharmacokinetics and biodistribution¹⁸. Most derivatives of Hoechst 33342 which are reported earlier¹⁹ having the mono-substitution at *para* or *meta* position of phenyl ring, which kept whole molecules to planar structures. To our knowledge, no literature related to the proposed substituted groups, having different aliphatic chains as substituents, in piperazine of bisbenzimidazole as the derivatives of Hoechst were reported so far.

In present study, our data shows AT specificity in the minor groove towards d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ oligomer. Most minor groove binders possess the binding preference for A/T over G/C sequences, and the preference of A/T sequences mainly arises from the following factors. Firstly, the minor groove of A/T rich sequences is narrower than G/C rich sequences. Thus, it provides tighter contact with groove binders, causing stronger van der Waals interactions. Secondly, the electrostatic potentials in the A/T rich regions are more negative than G/C rich regions at the floor of the DNA minor groove²⁰. Most minor groove binders are positively charged and their cationic nature can be balanced by a negatively charged A/T base-pair floor. Thirdly, the exocyclic 2-amino group of guanine sterically blocks the groove binder from gaining close

contact to the GC region floor and hydrogen bonding. A possibility with groove binding molecules is that they can be extended to fit over many base-pairs along the groove and have high sequence specific recognition of nucleic acids. We have synthesized four ligands MMPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF (Fig. 1) by substituting one end with different length of aliphatic side chains and other end with tri-fluoro methyl group in phenyl ring with the methodology reported earlier²¹. We have observed the aliphatic chain length favors the binding affinity in the minor groove with a specific DNA sequence.

Fig. 1. Structure of ligands.

In view of the intensive research done in the field of medicinal chemistry to improve the molecular recognition pattern of DNA targeting agents, we have synthesized four novel analogs of Hoechst 33342. The inherent simplicity of the strategy allowed us to synthesize by varying substitutions at phenyl ring as well as piperazine rings. With different biophysical techniques like UV Spectroscopy, Circular Dichroism (CD), and Fluorescence, we established that the novel synthesized ligands have potent binding affinity towards minor groove of AT-rich duplex DNA and their affinity was correlated with the data obtained from molecular docking. The decamer sequence was converged to the B-DNA type of duplex during docking which is also verified by CD. We have evaluated DNA binding and sequence recognition of four bisbenzimidazole derivatives. In order to investigate DNA binding, absorption and fluorescence titration measurements were performed, which gave an estimate of the equilibrium affinity. Data obtained from DNA melting and CD titrations provided further insight into the nature of the interaction. Molecular docking study validated the observed data obtained from spectroscopy. The binding study between the DNA and the ligands, thereby offers scope for better understanding of the modes of DNA recognition.

Experimental

Material:

Hoechst 33342 (trihydrochloride salt) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich Pvt. Ltd. (USA). The compounds discussed here (MMPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF) were synthesized (Scheme S1) according to the earlier published report²¹. Stock solutions of all ligands (10 mM) were prepared in HPLC-grade water. We have synthesized hydrochloride salt of all four ligands by passing HCl gas in the methanolic solutions of ligands to increase solubility. The self-complementary oligonucleotides, synthesized on the 4 μ M scale by Sigma Aldrich Pvt. Ltd., were received in the lyophilized form. The synthetic oligomers were supplied in purified form via 16% PAGE in 7 M urea, supplemented with an electrophoretogram exhibiting a single band and a stated purity of 99%. All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Sample preparation:

The self-complementary oligonucleotide was stored at -20°C and used without further purification. The concentration of oligonucleotides was determined with the help of UV-Vis spectroscopy using its molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) by measuring the absorbance at 260 nm at room temperature following the method described earlier. The ϵ values used for the 10 mer oligonucleotide d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ is 100800 $\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. Stock solutions of the oligomer were prepared by directly dissolving the lyophilized powder in MilliQ water. DNA duplex was prepared from equimolar solution of monomers in buffer (20 mM sodium cacodylate, 0.1 M NaCl), heated to 95°C for 5 min and then cooled slowly to room temperature and to 4°C temperature. Ligands concentration was determined spectroscopically in 1 cm path length cuvettes using the molar extinction coefficients ($\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$). Working stocks were prepared afresh before each experiment from these by dilution with buffer. DNA-Drug interaction was monitored using spectroscopic techniques from changes in absorption and fluorescence spectra upon binding at 10°C .

DNA binding study using different spectroscopic methods:

Ligands that interact with DNA base pairs can lead to marked changes in the electronic properties of nucleic acid bases, therefore techniques such as ultraviolet-visible absorption and circular dichroism spectroscopy can be particu-

larly useful. Tendency and magnitude of peak shifted and hypo/hyperchromicity of the band is useful for assessing the binding mode and binding constants. DNA-ligand interaction was monitored using spectroscopic techniques from changes in absorption spectra upon binding at 10°C . The 5 μ M solutions of MMPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF were prepared in sodium cacodylate buffer (20 mM, 100 mM NaCl, pH 7.2) and the absorption spectra were recorded using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Cary Varian 300) in the presence or absence of DNA (synthetic oligonucleotides) at ligand/DNA ratio, $r = 0.2$ to 3. A Scatchard plot of r/C_f versus r was obtained, where r is the ratio of bound ligand concentration to the total DNA concentrations in base pairs and C_f is the concentration of free ligand from the titration data.

Besides absorption titration, we performed thermal denaturation experiments of DNA duplex with and without the ligands. The absorbance versus temperature curve is called melting curve, and the midpoint of transition is called melting temperature (T_m). The T_m of the DNA is sensitive to its double helix stability and the binding of ligand to DNA alters the T_m depending strength of interactions. The thermal denaturation experiments were performed on a Cary Varian 300 spectrophotometer equipped with a peltier thermo programmer. Stopped quartz cuvettes of 1 cm optical path length and 1 mL volume were used for the measurements. The temperature of the cell holder was increased from 10 to 95°C and vice versa at a rate of $0.2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. A Teflon-coated temperature probe, attached to a cuvette system, measured the sample temperature. The sample solutions were overlaid with paraffin oil to prevent evaporation. T_m experiments of DNA (2.5 μ M) in the absence and presence of ligands, were carried out at a wavelength of 260 nm as a function of temperature at ligand: DNA ratio of 1:1 per synthetic oligomer. DNA without compounds was used as a control. The thermal melting temperature (T_m) was determined by plotting the first derivative of the absorbance with respect to temperature (dA_{260}/dT).

CD spectroscopy can be a very powerful technique for investigation of small molecule interactions with nucleic acids. A large number of small molecules are achiral and therefore do not give CD signal because the two components of polarized light (left and right) are absorbed equally. However, upon interactions with nucleic acids, an induced CD

effect is observed. Induced CD is defined as ellipticity observed in the absorption region of achiral guest chromophores. Stacking interactions (electronic transitions) between achiral ligands (guest) and chiral nucleic acids (host) can lead to induced CD. Changes in melting temperature, modes of interactions, and assembly of unstable structures, binding constants determination, and stoichiometry of ligand-nucleic acid binding are some of the drug-DNA parameters that we have been able to determine by using spectroscopic techniques. CD experiments were carried out at 10°C using a Jasco J-810 spectropolarimeter. The spectra were recorded at a scan rate of 50 nm/min from 600–200 nm wave length and an average of 3 scans was taken. The induced CD signal (ICD) of the ligands was monitored in the 340–350 nm range. Measurements were done in quartz cuvettes of 1 cm optical path length. A constant concentration of DNA (10 μ M) for d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ was triturated with increasing concentrations of the ligand. Between each ligand addition an interval of 5 min was maintained and samples were mixed by pipetting up and down with a Pasteur pipette.

Fluorescence experiments were conducted using a Cary Varian Eclipse instrument at 10°C. A solution of ligand (serially diluted to working concentrations) was excited at its respective λ_{max} (slits of 5 nm), and resulting emission curves (from 370 to 700 nm) were recorded after serial additions of a concentrated DNA solution (0.2 μ M). Here also, we determined Scatchard plot of r/C_f versus r as discussed earlier.

Docking protocol:

Crystal structure of d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ DNA was constructed as B-DNA type from the web server (<http://www.scfbio.com>). Ligands (Hoechst 33342, MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF) were viewed in Viewer Lite software²² and then brought to their energetically minimized structures by Gaussian utilizing a conjugate gradient method with 6-31G MP2 force field. Afterwards, the DNA and optimized structures of ligands were converted to required pdbqt format using Autodock Tools 1.5.4²³. Autodock tools (ADT) were used to merge nonpolar hydrogens of DNA and assign atomic charges. Nonpolar hydrogen of each compound was merged and rotatable bonds were assigned. Grid maps were generated for each atom type using AUTOGRID. An active site box of 50×50×50 Å³ with grid spacing of 0.375 Å was created and placed at the center of DNA structure. Docking calculations were carried out using Lamarckian genetic algo-

rihm. A population of random individuals (population size: 150) was used with 2500000 energy evaluations. A maximum number of 27000 generations with mutation rate of 0.02 were used. Fifty independent runs for compound were performed with target protein. The resulting positions were clustered according to a root-mean-square criterion of 0.5 Å. Finally, the best conformation of the ligand with the lowest binding energy was selected to analyze the probable interaction i.e. DNA and minor groove binders taken here. Molecular visualizations were carried out in Chimera²⁴ in the whole study.

Results and discussion

DNA binding of novel ligands:

We are interested in understanding the molecular recognition process between the groove binding ligands and DNA. There are two possible approaches for investigation of the molecular contacts between ligands and DNA; (i) Keep the receptor (DNA) structure unchanged and alter the ligand structure systematically, (ii) Retain the ligand structure unchanged and alters the receptor structure. Although both approaches could, in principle, lead to better understanding of specific interactions between the ligands and receptor, there is one main disadvantage with later. Any change in the DNA base sequence or structure would be expected to perturb DNA conformation, which would therefore influence the binding of the ligand to the receptor. To investigate the relative binding affinities and stoichiometries of the synthesized ligands, we carried out UV absorption, fluorescence and circular dichroism (CD) titration with A/T rich oligomer. Additionally we also checked the thermal stability of duplex DNA induced by the new synthesized molecules.

Binds uniformly with UV absorption titration:

To understand the DNA binding behavior of a ligand UV-Visible absorption spectroscopy is routinely used. In the present study, we have focused on the binding of four synthesized novel ligands (MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF) with duplex. We have shown the changes in the absorption spectra of above mentioned ligands when titrated against increasing amounts of DNA duplex d(GTTTAAAAC)₂. The UV absorption profile of ligands saturated with the DNA sequences, d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ has been summarized in Fig. 2. With duplex DNA, very little hypochromicity change was found. The maxima were ob-

Fig. 2. UV-detected binding of d(GTTTAAAC)₂ with (A) MPPMF, (B) APPMF, (C) BPPMF and (D) NNPMF. Small aliquots (5 μ L) of DNA (1 μ M) were added to a solution of the Ligand (1 mL of a 5 μ M solution). Scatchard plots of these above mentioned ligands at their maximum absorbance. Buffer: 20 mM sodium cacodylate, 100 mM NaCl (pH 7.2).

served around 343, 345, 347 and 350 nm for MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF respectively. The Scatchard plots (r/C_f vs r) so obtained were all linear which clearly indicate the possibility of one binding site for ligands. Scatchard plots are linear only for binding to independent and equivalent sites; any curvature in the plots indicates the existence of more than one type of binding site, ligand-ligand interactions, or neighbor exclusion effects.

The binding parameters have been summarized in the Table 1. The binding affinity of above mentioned ligand along with Hoechst 33342 with the 10 mer duplex was 2.0×10^7 , 3.0×10^8 , 5.0×10^8 and 7.0×10^7 M^{-1} respectively (Supplementary Fig. S1). The stoichiometry interaction of all ligands was near about 1. Addition of duplex solutions in ligand showed hypochromicity in all ligands, which clearly suggest that all ligands are capable to bind with duplex DNA. Successive

Table 1. Binding parameters obtained from UV-Vis titration experiments and melting temperature of DNA-ligand complexes

Ligand	Binding affinity with duplex DNA d(GT ₄ A ₄ C) ₂ (M^{-1}) K_a	Red shift (nm)	Melting temperature ^a (°C)	
			T_m	ΔT_m
 MPPMF	2.0×10^7	11	27	5
 APPMF	3.0×10^8	13	35	13
 BPPMF	5.0×10^8	16	40	18
 NNPMF	7.0×10^7	10	32	10
 Hoechst 33342	1.0×10^7	19	28	6

^aMelting temperature of d(GTTTAAAC)₂: 22°C.

Buffer used: 20m M sodium cacodylate, 100 mM NaCl (pH 7.2).

addition of duplex DNA until saturation of ligand MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF brings about a red shift 11, 13, 16 and 10 respectively with a hypochromicity, which suggests an interaction of ligands with DNA.

Benzimidazoles increase the thermal stability of duplex DNA:

After getting stoichiometry around 1, we performed UV-melting experiment of all four ligands along with Hoechst 33342 with d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ in same working buffer. Table 1 depicts the melting temperature of each duplex when those ligands bound with equimolar concentration of DNA. A gradual increase in the stability was found from MPPMF, APPMF to BPPMF with increasing carbon side chain. A maximum of 18°C increment in stability was observed with BPPMF whereas APPMF and MPPMF show 13 and 5°C respectively. The sigmoid curvatures (Fig. 3) found from all ligands with the duplex DNA used, proved proper minor groove binding with no deformation during duplex formation. This anticipated result prompted studies of the ligand-DNA complex by other spectroscopic methods, most notably circular dichroism (CD) and fluorescence titration.

Fig. 3. UV Melting temperature of d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ with MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF in 1:1 ratio. Buffer: 20 mM sodium cacodylate, 100 mM NaCl (pH 7.2).

Circular dichroism shows proper B-DNA signature:

CD spectroscopy provides a powerful tool to detect and characterize the complexes of DNA duplexes with Hoechst 33342, as with other derivatives, either the duplex DNA nor

the ligand alone exhibited CD signals at the wavelengths of absorbance of the ligand, but the asymmetry in the optical properties of the ligands due to the effect of the DNA field results in distinctive induced CD spectra of the complexes at those wavelengths. We found the ideal CD signature pattern of duplex, a positive band around 280 nm and a negative band around 245 nm (Fig. 4). This signifies the duplex DNA exist in B-form during the titration and throughout the all experiment the signature pattern did not change a bit, implies the rigidity of the conformations of DNA. All four ligands (MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF) bind to the duplex DNA as in all three cases the increment of CD signals found and the ligand might be bound in the major or minor groove of DNA without affecting the groove conformations as we did not find any shift of band in all experiments. The induced bands due to complexation of the ligands with d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ are centered around 320–380 nm. All the spectra are characterized by isobestic points—different for the different ligands up to drug/oligomer, ratio = 5:1 and cross-over point for the ligands-DNA complexes changes with addition of ligands.

Fluorescence titration indicates significant binding to duplex DNA:

The fluorescence spectrum of free ligand contains a single broad emission band centered at 496–511 nm. Halogenated bisbenzimidazoles (here MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF) have quite weak fluorescence as compared to non-halogenated parent analog Hoechst 33342. All the ligands showed the quenching in range of 25–30 μM concentration (Fig. 5).

The established DNA minor groove binder, Hoechst 33342 was discovered to display multiple modes of binding to polymeric DNA (especially with AT rich DNA). Upon binding to DNA, fluorophore exhibits a significant fluorescence enhancement, due to the loss of solvent exposure upon snugly binding (van der Waals and H-bonding forces) within the DNA groove. Ligands showed single emission maxima in presence of DNA. Three ligands (MPPMF, APPMF and BPPMF) shows red shift 80, 30 and 30 nm respectively with d(GTTTAAAAC)₂ whereas for NNPMF shows a moderate

Fig. 4. Circular dichroism detected binding of $d(\text{GTTTAAAAC})_2$ with MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF. Small aliquots (5 μL) of Ligand (5 μM) were added to a solution of the Ligand (1 mL of a 10 μM solution). Buffer: 20 mM sodium cacodylate, 100 mM NaCl (pH 7.2).

red shift of 10 nm. There are remarkable increase in fluorescence of above mentioned ligands upon binding to the duplex at drug/oligomer ratio, $r = 0.2:1$. We determined their binding affinity with oligomeric duplex by Scatchard plots here too and the stoichiometries found to be around 1 which validated our absorption-titrations.

Minor groove binding shows by molecular docking:

To find the actual insight picture of the used ligands besides its parent analog we have done molecular docking of those ligands with the 3D structure of $d(\text{GTTTAAAAC})_2$ DNA. Each ligand was found to bind in the minor groove only along with Hoechst 33342 (Fig. 6). Thus, our docking method is validated as we found the same binding mode towards minor groove. Docked-DNA duplex here contained a major

groove and a minor groove in the duplex DNA used. In most of the cases, the binding mode was found as 5'-Pu-Pu-Py-Py. Adenine and thymine specific bindings were found in minor groove. A docking pattern was found to be followed in this respect as increasing of aliphatic carbon at piperazine end increases the binding affinity thus the docking score was found to be gradually increase from MPPMF (-6.21), APPMF (-6.62) to BPPMF (-7.54), besides incase of NNPMF it was found to be with a moderate score of -6.34. In all the cases tri-fluoro substituent at phenyl ring was remain constant and found to present mostly outside the minor groove and shows very little interaction with the phosphate backbone. The detailed docking scores and poses are depicted in Supporting Table 1. The interactive nucleotides are mainly identical with all four ligands as all four of them bind the same groove.

Fig. 5. Fluorescence-detected binding of $d(\text{GTTTAAAAC})_2$ with MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF. Small aliquots (5 μL) of DNA (0.2 μM) were added to a solution of the Ligand (3 mL of a 1 μM solution). Buffer: 20 mM sodium cacodylate, 100 mM NaCl (pH 7.2).

Fig. 6. 3D-Docked structure of Hoechst 33342, MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF with $d(\text{GTTTAAAAC})_2$ DNA.

Conclusion

In this manuscript, we studied binding affinity of bisbenzimidazole derivatives having different substitutions on piperazine nucleus towards AT rich DNA. The results suggest that increase of chain length at one end bind with differ-

ential affinity towards duplex DNA. This study deepened our understanding of ligand based minor groove binding in the following aspects: (a) Melting temperature and binding affinities indicate that BPPMF with longer aliphatic chain has higher binding affinity ($K_a = 5.0 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $\Delta T_m = 18^\circ\text{C}$) towards $d(\text{GTTTAAAAC})_2$ as compared to MPPMF and APPMF with shorter side chains; (b) The positive ICD bands obtained on DNA addition, for MPPMF, APPMF, BPPMF and NNPMF, indicate the strong DNA binding affinity of these ligands; (c) Fluorescence and CD revealed that these molecules bind to AT rich DNA with no change in conformation of B-DNA; (d) The docking study clearly showed that molecules with different substitution at the piperazine ring similarly sit in the narrower minor groove of AT rich oligonucleotides and the docking scores obtained correlate the data from spectroscopic techniques. The overall study might help

to develop understanding of molecule designing towards specific duplex DNA sequences.

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Supporting Information

Synthetic scheme for compound synthesis, UV titration and Scatchard plots of Hoechst 33342; with DNA and detail molecular docking data is available.

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